

Low Grade Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasm: Case Report of Three CasesMishra Omkar¹, Dewangan Manish², Gupta Parag³, Sahu Priya⁴¹DNB resident, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Hospital and Research Centre, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India, 490009^{2,3}Chief consultant, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Hospital and Research Centre, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India, 490009⁴Senior consultant, Department of Pathology, Jawaharlal Nehru Hospital and Research Centre, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India, 490009

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mishra Omkar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasm (AMN) belongs to a rare group of gastrointestinal malignancy. AMN with minimal cytological atypia on histopathology constitutes Low grade Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasm (LAMN). These are mostly incidental findings detected by histopathological examination post appendicectomy. We present three such cases presenting with vague abdominal pain with palpable lump in the right iliac fossa. After necessary hematological and radiological investigations, all of them underwent surgery. The postoperative period was uneventful. A diagnosis of Low grade Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasm was established based on histopathology in all patients. They are in regular follow-up with annual abdominopelvic CT and tumor markers with no notable complications.

Keywords: AMN; LAMN; PMP; CRS-HIPEC.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

AMN is found in approximately 0.3% of appendicectomy specimens [1, 2]. Classification systems for AMN are numerous, hence controversial [2].

A unified classification of AMN has been proposed by modified Delphi consultation, where AMN with minimal cytological atypia has been categorized as LAMN [3]. It is characterized by pushing rather than infiltrating lesions without evidence of breach [2, 3] with tenacious mucin as content.

In the case of perforation, mucin disseminates inside the peritoneal cavity with or without epithelial cells seeding, causing a syndrome known as Pseudomyxoma Peritonei (PMP) or Mucinous Ascites for which operative and postoperative management varies significantly [3,4].

Case report

Case-1: A 53-year-old male presented with vague right abdominal pain for one month. There was no history of vomiting, fever or weight loss. The vitals of the patient were within acceptable range on admission. An abdomen examination revealed a globular lump in the right iliac fossa. Haematological investigations were within normal limits.

Ultrasonography of the abdomen suggested a mucocele of the appendix. CECT Abdomen showed a cystic lesion of approximately 5*6 cm in the appendix with peripheral enhancement but no surrounding fat stranding (Fig 1(a, b)). On exploration, a cystic lesion of the appendix filled with mucinous material was found.

The base of the appendix and mesoappendix were involved (Fig 1(c)). Hence, a Right hemicolectomy was performed. Histopathology suggested LAMN on H&E stain (Fig 1(d)).

Figure 1: CECT abdomen (a) sagittal, (b) coronal section suggests a cystic lesion of the appendix (as shown by arrow) with peripheral enhancement and no evidence of surrounding fat stranding and adjacent bowel pathology, (c) Resected specimen shows appendix with involvement of its base and adjacent ileal segment, and (d) Histopathological slide shows complex papillary architecture with mucinous epithelial proliferation in 20x magnification and H&E stain.

Case-2: A 66-year-old female presented with recurrent vague pain in the abdomen with intermittent fever for 4 months. There was no associated vomiting or weight loss. On admission, the patient was afebrile. On per abdomen examination, it was suggestive of a lump in the right iliac fossa. All haematological investigations, including total leukocyte count, were normal. USG Abdomen showed an appendix of 9 cm in length and 4 cm in diameter filled with mucin with 10 mm calcification. CECT abdomen showed a chronic

cystic lesion of the appendix measuring approximately 4*4 cm with peripheral enhancement but no fat stranding surrounding it. (Fig 2(a)).

Diagnostic laparoscopy revealed a distended appendix (Fig 2(b)). Open appendicectomy was done since the base of the appendix and mesoappendix were not involved. (Fig 2(c)). LAMN was found on post appendicectomy histopathology (Fig 2(d)).

Figure 2: (a) Axial view of CECET abdomen shows a chronic cystic lesion of the appendix of 4*4 cm size, which shows peripheral enhancement but no surrounding fat stranding or adjacent bowel involvement, (b) Laparoscopic view demonstrates grossly distended appendix however no peritoneal collection noted, (c) Appendicectomy specimen shows cystic swelling of 10*4 cm but no base involvement, and (d) Histopathology, in 4x magnification and H&E stain, is suggestive of calcification and mucin deposition

Case-3: A 53-year-old male presented with vague right abdominal pain for 5 days. There was a previous history of similar episode but not associated with fever, vomiting or weight loss.

On abdominal examination, a lump was palpable in the right iliac fossa. Ultrasonography of the abdomen revealed a loculated collection in the right

iliac fossa with an appendicular mass of 1.7 cm in diameter (Fig 3(a)). The patient was subjected to diagnostic laparoscopy, which revealed a cystic lesion of the appendix with no evidence of mucin spillage (Fig 3(b)). Open appendectomy was performed, and the specimen was sent for histopathological examination, which suggested LAMN (Fig 3(d)).

Figure 3(a) Ultrasonography abdomen suggests appendicular mass of about 1.7 cm diameter with loculated collection in the right iliac fossa, **(b)** Laparoscopic view of appendix shows cystic lesion, but no mucin spillage is noted, **(c)** Appendicectomy specimen shows cystic swelling covering maximum portion of appendix with base and tip sparing, and **(d)** Histopathological studies demonstrate mucinous epithelial proliferation but no mucin in stroma seen in 10x magnification and H&E stain

All three patients had uneventful postoperative stays. All of them were followed up with colonoscopy to rule out primary colorectal lesions, which were negative for them. They are in regular follow-ups with annual abdominal CT scans and tumor markers such as CEA, CA-19-9, and CA-125 and are devoid of any complications.

Results and Discussion

In most cases, Low-grade Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasm (LAMN) is an incidental diagnosis [5]. It usually involves middle-aged persons who present to the hospital with chronic vague right abdominal pain and not necessarily with any associated symptoms.

Surgical management varies based on intraoperative findings and postoperative

histopathology reports. Appendectomy with excision of mesoappendix is the mainstay of treatment. Right Hemicolectomy is indicated in positive margins, appendiceal base involvement, extra-appendiceal extension, and invasive histology (adenocarcinoma) on histopathology [5]. In the case of PMP, post appendectomy Cytoreductive surgery with Heated Intraperitoneal Chemotherapy (CRS-HIPEC) is mandatory for long-term survival [4,5]. Follow-up colonoscopy is essential in LAMN patients to rule out rectal pathology. Annual low-dose abdominopelvic CT with tumor markers such as CEA, CA-19-9, and CA-125 is done per surveillance protocol for at least five years [3,6]. In our first case, Right Hemicolectomy was done owing to the involvement of the base of the appendix and the mesoappendix. The other two cases, however, were managed by appendectomy alone since no appendiceal base involvement or mucin spillage was evident.

Conclusion

Patients with LAMN usually present in the middle-aged group with chronic vague right abdominal pain. Since the pain is not excruciating and can be alleviated by analgesics in the early stages of the disease, patients don't seek medical opinion until it recurs a few more times. However, the risk of appendiceal perforation rises with increasing time due to continuous deposition of mucin and resulting appendicular distension. Perforation can lead to PMP, for which aggressive management is necessary and is often detrimental to the standard of living of the concerned patient. Therefore, public awareness, early diagnosis and prompt treatment are required.

Acknowledgment: The authors acknowledge the support and cooperation received from the host

institute for their research work. The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The authors declare that informed consent has been obtained from patients and their relatives.

Reference

1. Gonzalez HH, Herard K, Mijares MC. A rare case of low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm: a case report. *Cureus*. 2019 Jan 29; 11(1).
2. Li X, Zhou J, Dong M, Yang L. Management and prognosis of low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasms: a clinicopathologic analysis of 50 cases. *European Journal of Surgical Oncology*. 2018 Oct 1; 44(10):1640-5.
3. O'Connell PR, McCaskie AW, Sayers RD. *Bailey & Love's short practice of surgery*. CRC Press; 2023 Mar 30.
4. McDonald JR, O'Dwyer ST, Rout S, Chakrabarty B, Sikand K, Fulford PE, Wilson MS, Renehan AG. Classification of and cytoreductive surgery for low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasms. *Journal of British Surgery*. 2012 Jul; 99(7):987-92.
5. Townsend CM, Beauchamp RD, Evers BM, Mattox KL, editors. *Sabiston textbook of surgery: the biological basis of modern surgical practice*. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2016 Apr 22.
6. Xiao J, Li P, Liu W. Analysis of clinical characteristics of low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm (LAMN): a retrospective cohort study of 51 LAMN patients. *Journal of Investigative Surgery*. 2021 Aug 9; 34(7):721-7.